

THE IMPACT OF HUMAN RESOURCES MANAGEMENT PRACTICES IN ACHIEVING TOTAL QUALITY / A STUDY IN HEALTH CENTERS IN THE NORTHERN SECTOR JORDAN

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Abstract

This study seeks to clarify the relationship between the role of human resources management practices in achieving total quality in health centers in the northern sector, and to provide a systematic perception of the most important practices related to human resources that affect achieving total quality. It is represented in the quality of service in health centers in the northern sector through (employee relations, training and development, motivation, guidance and guidance). This has affected the improvement of the performance of workers in health centers and the satisfaction of service recipients. The study population formed all medical staff (service providers) in the health centers in the directorates of the northern sector of the Ministry of Health, and this information was taken from the directorates of health of Irbid governorate, and a sample of workers in all centers of the northern sector amounted to (100), and all of them were considered valid for analysis. The findings of this study showed that there is an average impact of training and development of workers in achieving total quality in health centers in Irbid Governorate, but it did not reach the level of statistical significance. While the impact of the employee's relations in achieving total quality was high, the study also showed that incentives have a clear motivation to improve total quality, and there is an average but not statistically significant impact of the element of guidance and guidance in achieving total quality in health centers in Irbid Governorate. In conclusion, this study concluded with a set of recommendations, which were drawn in light of the results, the most important of which was, conducting training courses to develop workers and increase their efficiency to achieve total quality in health centers. And Provide guidelines to enhance the efficiency of performance and quality of work for new employees.

Keywords: Human Resources Management, Practices in Achieving Total Quality, Health Centers.

INTRODUCTION

Organizations at this time face wide challenges in a world characterized by change and competition aimed at providing the best services and goods to the beneficiaries, which prompted many organizations to keep pace with the times and change traditional administrative methods and search for new concepts that enable the organization to achieve its goals efficiently and effectively.

The subject of total quality management has gained global attention during the last three decades of the last century, and the beginning of this century, and the subject of quality management is one of the basic and essential elements to achieve excellence in the production of goods and services, and this interest has accompanied an accelerated development in the concepts of quality management or continuous improvement of quality, and many countries of the world have developed national models and awards for quality and excellence, In Jordan, the King Abdullah II Award for Excellence was established to achieve competitive advantage in Jordanian organizations and institutions.

The concept of quality varies according to the quality of outputs, and the dimensions of the concept are related to the nature of the organization, whether it is an industrial or service organization, where the industrial organization is interested in the tangible aspects of product quality, while service organizations are interested in the intangible aspects of quality.

The total quality tool is one of the contemporary administrative methods, which has been adopted by most of the public and private production and service organizations, which must apply its principles and concepts in its activities, provide the means and mobilize the capabilities to apply and mature it, due to its direct link to the human element.

Interest in the issue of quality management in the health sector began in the early seventies of the last century, and human resources are one of the most valuable resources in achieving total quality, and that continuous improvement of the knowledge, skills, values and behaviors of health care providers can only be achieved through the development and training of human cadres in health institutions and health centers, in order to achieve operational efficiency, reduce costs and excellence in providing health care, which requires providing the right number and diversity of employees in order to be able to do with its tasks to the fullest.

The problem questions of the study

revolves around the extent to which the dimensions of total quality are achieved, represented in the quality of service (time, accuracy of delivery, knowledge, handling, consistency, accessibility, accuracy of delivery, response) in health centers in the northern sector through the practices of human resources strategies (employee relations, training and development, motivation, and guidance). This has affected the improvement of the performance of workers in health centers and the satisfaction of service recipients. The problem of the study can be formulated in the form of the following questions:

The first question: To what extent does training and development of human resources affect the achievement of total quality in health centers in the northern sector?

The second question: What is the role of motivation for human resources in achieving total quality in health centers in the northern sector?

The third question: What is the role of guidance for human resources in achieving total quality in health centers in the northern sector?

The Fourth question: What is the role of employee's relations in achieving total quality in health centers in the northern sector?

The importance of the study

lies in the fact that it seeks to clarify the relationship between the role of human resources practice and its impact in achieving total quality in health centers in the northern sector, achieving satisfaction of the service provider and recipients, and providing a systematic perception of the most important practices related to human resources affecting achieving total quality.

Objectives of the study

This study aims to clarify the relationship between the role of human resources practices and their impact in achieving total quality in health centers in the northern sector through:

- Introducing the concept and importance of total quality management and its impact on raising the level of job performance.

- Highlighting the great need to activate the role of information technology in the health center to speed up the completion of work.
- Activating the concept of total quality and attracting qualified employees and placing them in the right place without bias to work on human resources - development Statement of the impact of human resources development in achieving internal consumer satisfaction (health care provider).

Study Design: This study relied on the descriptive analytical approach, the field study method, and through the preparation and development of its questionnaire as a main tool for data collection.

Data collection methods

- a) Secondary data collection: Secondary data was obtained through the researcher's review of the literature from books, periodicals and previous studies related to the subject of the study.
- b) Means of primary data collection: This study used the questionnaire as a means of collecting primary data.

Tests for the measuring instrument

- A. Validity, is defined as the process of ensuring that the instrument (scale) used actually measures the phenomenon it was designed to measure. The authenticity of the content of the measurement tool (questionnaire) used in this study was ascertained, as it was presented after the development of its initial form to three arbitrators from the faculty members at Jerash and Yarmouk University, to ensure that it covered the basic aspects of the topic, its clarity, and the integrity of its formulation and contents. The tool was then modified based on their observations in deleting some phrases, modifying and adding new phrases, and reformulating some paragraphs, to become clearer and more understandable among the members of the study sample, to be more honest in measuring the subject of this study.
- B. Reliability, the stability of the instrument used in the study was confirmed by extracting the Cronbach Alpha coefficient for internal consistency, Cronbach Alpha for multi-point scale. In order to ensure that the measurement tool does not obtain false data, if the same study is repeated and using the same tool in the same conditions in which it was used for the first time, and the value of this coefficient reached (0.81) for the all dimensions.

Hypotheses of the study

The first hypothesis: There is a statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for training and development in achieving total quality in health centers.

The second hypothesis: There is a statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of motivation in achieving total quality in health centers.

The third hypothesis: There is a statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of guidance in achieving total quality in health centers.

The fourth hypothesis: There is a statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of employee's relations in achieving total quality in health centers.

Population of the study and sample

The study population formed all medical staff (service providers) in health centers in the directorates of the northern sector of the Ministry of Health, the sample was selected to be from the Directorate of Health of Irbid Governorate, and its health centers amounting to (28) centers and divided into three centers, which are comprehensive health centers, primary health centers and sub-health centers, this

category was chosen as it has the ability to understand the variables of the study and its pillars and has extensive experience in the health sector centers, and this ensures that the study sample has knowledge sufficient to provide effective and real answers about previous experiences in health work.

This information was taken from the Irbid Governorate Health Directorate, which contains all the information about the health centers. A sample of workers in all centers of the northern sector amounting to (100) was selected, and all of them were considered valid for analysis.

Related studies

(Yang, C, 2025), The Impact of Human Resource Management Practices on the Implementation of Total Quality Management: An Empirical Study on High-Tech Firms: This empirical research explores how HRM practices influence the implementation of TQM in high-tech companies. It highlights HR planning, leadership development, and training as critical drivers in adopting TQM, with hiring and performance appraisal contributing structurally to corporate reputation and satisfaction.

(Ababneh, A., M., Jarah ,2024), The Role of Human Resources Management in the Development of Total Quality Management in the Public and Private Sectors in Jordan:

This quantitative study conducted in Jordan among 235 HR professionals (public and private sectors) used random sampling and structured questionnaires to analyze the relationship between HRM practices (planning, training, performance appraisal, and incentives) and TQM. It found that HR planning, training, and performance appraisal significantly contribute to TQM development, while incentives showed a weaker link.

(Alam, S., Jumady, E., 2024), Integrating Total Quality Management with Strategic, Operational, and Human Resource Management:

A Qualitative Exploration of Synergies for Enhanced Organizational Performance: Using a systematic review methodology, this study synthesizes literature on integrating TQM with strategic, operational, and HRM practices. It identified benefits such as improved operational efficiency and higher employee engagement and discussed challenges like change resistance and cultural barriers.

(Nson, Y. D, 2024), Management by Walking About in Achieving Organizational Excellence: The Role of Total Quality Management:

This conceptual review explores how Management by Walking Around (MBWA) contributes to organizational excellence through TQM mediation. MBWA positively influences performance, and its effect is amplified when mediated by robust TQM frameworks.

(E3S Web of Conferences, 2024), Do Human Resources Management Practices Create Quality Workplaces and Enhance Organizational Performance?

This paper offers a systematic overview of evolving HRM practices aimed at creating high-quality, sustainable work environments. It concludes that modern HRM interventions significantly improve both employee welfare and organizational performance.

(Arishi and Al-Tarawneh, 2020), entitled. Human resources planning and its impact on the application of total quality management at Jazan University. The study aimed to identify the impact of human resources planning on the application of total quality management at Jazan University, and to identify the reality of human resources planning practices and the application of total quality management at Jazan University. The present study used the descriptive analytical approach using the data collection tool. The results showed that support and follow-up, and plans variables were the most achieved, while analyzing human needs variable was the least achieved. It also showed that the most achieved variable in the application of total quality the support of senior management variable, followed by

making decisions based on comprehensive information variable, and the least achieved variable was focusing on the customer.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

In light of the changes and challenges facing companies in general and human resources management in particular, such as scientific progress, technical development, globalization, diversity of skills and different workforce mix, challenges have been created that require different roles for the human resources function, and impose keeping pace with the stages of organizational development, adopting more modern and effective management methods in various activities, and qualifying the human resource as a vital source. (Saida, 2018).

Human resource management is about the ability to generate new knowledge with innovative effects, created through daily practices performed by practitioners at all levels of the company, and these practices have objectives, which include reducing the cost of human resources services or improving productivity (Bissola & Imperatori, 2013).

Organizations seek to achieve total quality management to meet the challenges of the surrounding environment, as it is based on the need to develop and improve performance levels by building an organizational culture that makes each worker realize that quality with inputs, processes and outputs is a major goal. Organizations have begun to apply TQM strategies as a system or philosophy based on a set of principles that focused directly on both customer satisfaction and continuous improvement processes, and in order for organizations to overcome and face each of these challenges, as well as to face and meet the growing demand for high-quality services and products, where continuous improvement includes all activities and processes practiced by the organization, as well as focusing on workers in various departments and focusing on the element of flexibility, and doing the required tasks correctly. From the first time, through all the main tools used by the organization's management to meet these challenges. (Garvin, 2014).

Also, human resources are considered one of the most important assets owned by organizations, and the most influential in productivity, and with their availability, the objectives of the organization can be achieved, so these organizations must take into account when using their human resources, the benefit and cost that can be achieved, and these changes have created new concepts related to the quality of products provided to customers, and thus prompted the organization to develop the products and services it provides through the adoption of a modern administrative concept through which it can achieve efficiency and excellence in performance, and it is known Human resources are the main pillar in the productive processes that the organization must start with to achieve a change that ensures its development and continuity. (Evans & Lindsay, 2014). Therefore, organizations have begun to adopt modern management concepts related to human resources management and total quality management to meet the changes and challenges facing the organization, as it is based on foundations based on continuous development of performance in terms of building an organizational culture for all its employees, based on product quality, and using all resources available to organizations and providing the product in the correct and appropriate manner.

As it is known, human resources management is one of the most important administrative functions, because of its focus on the human resource, which is one of the most valuable resources possessed by the department, which enables organizations to attract the necessary competencies capable of meeting current and future needs. (Dissler, 2013).

Human resources can contribute to achieving the goals of the organization, depending on efficiency, capabilities and experience, as well as attention to the foundations and principles that help to benefit from the organization's personnel, in order to succeed the organization's efforts to achieve its goals.

Human resources management is the department responsible for increasing the effectiveness of human resources in organizations to achieve the desired goals for the individual, the organization and society, as human resources represent the individuals employed by the organization to carry out various tasks, duties and jobs in exchange for wages, salaries, incentives and other rewards. (Serafi, 2013).

Dissler (2013) defined human resource management as "a department that includes policies and practices related to the selection of working individuals to be hired after a trade-off. The researcher defines human resources management as the main tasks that are concerned with dealing with the human element in organizations, which include planning, task analysis, job training, recruitment, selection and appointment, training and evaluation, compensation and incentives, in order to achieve the goals of the organization.

Daft (2014) argues that the failure of business organizations and the failure to put a person in a job that is not suitable for their skills and qualifications, will negatively affect the success and survival of business organizations.

Human resources planning in general means quantitative and qualitative estimation of the future needs of all types and levels of the workforce during a certain period of time, drawing strategies to meet those needs in a timely manner, so that this is on scientific grounds in light of the current situation, determining its dimensions, extrapolating the past, investigating expected future variables, and developing assumptions, alternatives and predictions. Workforce planning is part of the organization's overall strategic planning and is closely related to it, and proper workforce planning depends on understanding the organization's goals, philosophy and scope of work, workforce planning is closely related to many other human resources activities, such as job analysis, classification and evaluation, recruitment and recruitment programs, training and development. (Al-Salem and Harshoush, 2012).

Al-Serafi (2013) indicates that attracting and recruitment is the set of activities of the organization to search and attract candidates to fill job vacancies in it in a timely manner, and the recruitment function also includes meeting the needs, desires, abilities and interests of candidates for jobs, and thus attracting provides the opportunity for the organization and its applicants to choose each other according to their interests.

Training defines career development as a process aimed at improving and increasing the efficiency of employees to achieve the overall goals of society, through the acquisition of information and knowledge. (Noe, 2015).

Al-Hiti (2010) believes that training and career development is a process in which employees acquire information and skills that contribute to achieving better performance levels, to achieve goals closely related to the development processes of human resources.

The compensation and incentive function is concerned with the precise determination of the value and importance of the function performed by the individual, and with determining the level of pay grades for each job. (Renzl & Matzler, 2012).

Human resources are one of the most important resources that the organization needs, as other resources do not work within human resources, and human resources are part of the management concerned with the affairs of individuals working in terms of recruitment, qualification, training and development of competencies, as well as the description of their work. Desler (2013) defined it as "a set of practices and policies required to implement various activities related to the human aspects that the administration needs to exercise its functions to the fullest. Tayeb and Riai (2018) believes, it is "the art of attracting, selecting, hiring, developing their capabilities and developing their skills, and

creating the appropriate organizational conditions in terms of quantity and quality, to extract the best of their energies and encourage them to exert as much effort and giving as possible. "And defined by Joudeh (2010), as an administrative function that helps managers to attract, select, train and develop members in the organization.

Human resources are also concerned with the human dimension in organizations. After reviewing the multiple concepts of human resources management, we see that it is a series of procedures and foundations aimed at organizing individuals to obtain the maximum possible benefit from human competencies, and extract their best energies through the functions of planning, attracting, selection, appointment, training, evaluation, financial and moral incentives.

In the health sector, human resources are one of the most valuable resources of the health center. The Center must ensure that it has the right variety of staff in order to be able to carry out its mission to the fullest. It is necessary to write a job description that clearly defines the roles and responsibilities of each job, and qualified individuals who have the appropriate amount of experience for their positions are defined, awareness preparation must be done for employees in health centers, and many health care workers need to receive training and awareness about how to deal with people with disabilities.

The importance of human resource management

With regard to the use of the term human resources management, (Saleh, 2006) indicated that the term may refer to the following:

- Human resources management as activities practiced in order to provide, develop and maintain human resources.
- Human resources management as an administrative unit performs these activities as part of the functions of the organization.
- Human resource management as a profession in its own right, where there are many professional associations that bring together in their membership human resources practitioners.
- Human resources management as a scientific specialization as there are many universities that grant bachelor's, master's and doctoral degrees in human resources.
- Human resources management as a training program organized and implemented by many specialized institutes and training center.

Main activities of human resources management. (Alhiti, 2010).

Human Resource Planning, Recruitment and Selection, Organizing Administrative Structure, Training & Development, Benefits & Compensation, and Performance Management, Employees Relations.

Human Resource Planning: Here we come to the details of the human resource planning process. Human resources are concerned with obtaining the best performance and appointing the best candidates, the planning process here is responsible for evaluating the available resources, planning the human resources required in the future, and determining how.?, Either by developing existing individuals or bringing in others, or whether relying on permanent or temporary employment – depending on the economic feasibility and strategy of the company.

Looking for the right person, comes the recruitment process, which is the process responsible for finding the right – and if possible unique – employee and attracting them to work for the organization.

The hiring process is really a very delicate process because it is expensive and the error in it is very difficult to fix.

Recruitment and Selection: What channels are available for job advertising? Now the internet has become one of the main means of labor demand, especially if the job requires highly technical candidates. There are also recruitment companies and hiring by current employees Employee Referral, hiring directly from schools and universities, internal advertising in the institution or advertising in newspapers. Each of these methods has its advantages and disadvantages and the human resources department must determine the methods that are compatible with the company's strategies.

A good question to ask to think about is here, which is more useful? the employee who corresponds to the requirements of the job, or the one who corresponds to the personality of the manager?

Really that question is one of the difficult, because there is no clear answer to it. If the job has a lot of freedom and creativity, it is perhaps better for the employee to agree with the manager, because the disorder may negatively affect performance, but for clearly defined jobs and tasks, it is better to hire someone who complies with the system. In general, it is better for large organizations to focus on employees who meet their requirements, as those institutions are well organized, so that the field of solo playing is limited. In order for the huge machine to spin, each gear has to play its role well. In the end, there is no specific rule for that, but it was a point worth standing on.

Organizing Administrative Structure: One of the complex tasks of human resources management is to organize the administrative structure of the company, and that process aims for several goals, including controlling responsibilities and tasks, reducing duplication between processes, organizing the transfer of orders from leadership to employees and transferring reports in the reverse direction, as well as aiming to provide career growth opportunities for individuals to urge them to exert more effort and aims to eliminate unnecessary tasks.

Training & Development: For some employees, the training and development process is the main point when judging the human resources management in the companies they work for, because it means improving skills and thus increasing personal value. The training and development process seeks to improve the ability of individuals to perform the tasks assigned to them by increasing their knowledge, the way they perform jobs and improving their behavior within the company. The manager usually chooses the right training but there are cases where the human resource department makes the choice as well as in other cases the employee chooses the right training for him.

Benefits & Compensation: The most important part of all for employees, which is called the Benefits and Compensation, which is the branch responsible for determining the compensation that the employee receives for his work, either in material form or in the form of alternative benefits such as additional vacations, car, phone, or other benefits that are indirectly added to the employee's income. Each company has a different philosophy of compensating employees, with some paying only what they have to pay, while others paying a lot above the market price.

Among the factors affecting the evaluation of material compensation: skills, experience, responsibilities given to the employee, profits, as well as the nature of the work, its geographical distance, the employee's performance, the size of the company and its activities.

Performance Management: Also, one of the main tasks of human resources management is performance evaluation, which may worsen for several reasons, including the weakness of the employee's abilities, the absence of training, the absence of discipline or the absence of guidance. To improve performance, the employee must take the hand and make the improvement voluntarily, but if this is not possible due to the employee's refusal or impossibility, such improvement must be

imposed involuntarily. The last task of the Human Resources Department is to deal with unions that speak on behalf of workers to ensure their rights.

Perhaps human resources management is one of the most difficult and enjoyable branches of management, because of its close association with the most important production tools, which is the employee or worker, and perhaps the decisions coming from the human resources department are the most influential on workers in any company, and this is noticed when you find that the news coming from there may reach employees in a few minutes.

Employees Relations: Any organization seeking additional competitive advantage must adopt an outstanding HR management strategy. The cornerstone of HRM strategy is the relationship between manager and employee. Some studies confirm that the most important reason that pushes employees to resign is the line manager, not income, better opportunity, or other reasons. Since the line manager is the most influential element, human resource management focuses on developing the way managers think about their employees, so that the relationship turns – or develops – into something like a partnership rather than dependency, because partnership means more responsibility and means more passion towards work and therefore more productivity. Where the human resources department includes activities, related to dealing with the organization's employees and working to improve relations with them, as well as activating communications and ensuring that the open-door policy is followed, this activity also includes preparing and distributing books for new employees and educating workers about the prevailing laws and regulations Employee relations are tasks that many do not realize the importance of, just as the company needs external marketing, it also needs internal marketing. The company always needs to go towards internal dialogues with employees so that it can know the extent of employee satisfaction and so that it can communicate effectively with them, which raises production efficiency.

Total Quality Management

Total Quality Management (TQM) is central to all competition strategies developed by the organization to satisfy customers, the global competition has forced companies to think of new methods and means to win competition. Therefore, organizations must give value to the products or services provided and ensure quality. One of the most prominent concepts of quality management is the method that is based on developing the performance of organizations by building an organizational culture, that makes quality its primary goal in serving and satisfying the beneficiary. The development of this concept is due to the early pioneers in this field such as: Deming, Goran, Crosby, Ishikawa and others. (Jaboa, 2009).

The holistic concept of quality: it is to meet the desires and expectations of customers (external and entering). Total quality and total quality management: two common expressions in the contemporary language and express a global trend that controls the thought and actions of the people of management at their levels, and governs many management decisions in all fields In view of the transformations and developments that the world has witnessed and is still witnessing, especially in the economic aspect, from a noticeable increase in the number of institutions in different fields of activity, as well as the liberalization of foreign trade, all factors have led to an increase in competition between producers and increased their fear, and push them to search for the means that It enables them to maintain market share, as well as obtain competitive superiority both locally and internationally. The way to do this was to adopt the so-called Total Quality Management and qualify for ISO certification. (Almaani, 2010). Behind the application of the total quality program, there is the human element, as it is the savior element and is charged with reaching the achievement of the goals, since this element is the basis, what is the position it enjoys in the total quality program and ISO standards? As an answer to this problem, it can be said:

Total Quality Management gives great importance to the management of human resources, as it provides a set of principles to achieve quality in work and thus quality as a whole. The management of human resources, like the rest of the institution's functions, is represented by some ISO standards. The meaning of quality: is appropriate to use and is represented in: Low failure rate, reduced damaged, Reduced customer complaints, speeding up the provision of services to customers, Reduced need for testing and inspection, improve performance, Success in sales development, Success in reducing costs. (Altaie, 2008). Total quality is an entrance to a continuous comprehensive development that includes all stages of performance, and is the responsibility of each individual in the organization from senior management, management, sections and work teams in order to satisfy the needs and expectations of the customer, its scope includes all stages of operation and even dealing with the customer selling and serving any after-sales services. Total quality is based on: Preparing a quality improvement strategy that is no longer confined to production management, defining quality standards or levels, involve all possible individuals, maintain professionalism, Motivate workers. (Evans and Lindsay, 2014).

The philosophy of total quality management looks at the organization not only as a technical system, but as a social system that contains individuals, and therefore the aspects associated with the trends of ambitions, motives, behaviors and interaction between groups in the reality of work are also of interest; it also believes that the human element is the strongest and most important basis for the success of management, and the quality of work is an essential part of the concept of total quality.(Altaie, 2008).

The role of human resources management in the application of total quality management.

The Florida Power and Electricity Production Company's Experiment: (Dessler, 2013). Lessons learned from the Florida Power and Electricity Production Company, and the role played by the Human Resources Department in improving the company's quality, including:

- 1) Ensure that all teams work according to the established policy, to ensure that the efforts made are aligned with the objectives of the company.
- 2) Do not form independent teams to improve quality, but try to design in parallel, noting that such teams are kept away from the formal command chain.
- 3) Do not treat the quality improvement program as a goal in itself, but rather a continuous and organized means of performing work at a high level of quality.
- 4) Training is an indispensable necessity, as the quality improvement program does not achieve a high level of success except through continuous training of employees.
- 5) Providing employees with the necessary skills to analyze and solve problems.
- 6) The need to take into account the selection of quality workers who possess values and principles consistent with the requirements of the application of quality principles.
- 7) Do not always focus on increasing productivity, but pay attention to quality, quality and productivity are linked.
- 8) Permanent encouragement of employees, by satisfying their needs, knowing that it is not necessary to be material needs, but may be moral, and when employees in Florida were asked about the unsatisfied needs, they did not say a lack of funds, but they pointed to the need to take their proposals into account, and that the supervisors appreciate what they are doing.
- 9) Senior management should take into account the modification of the principles and concepts underlying traditional methods as a first step.

Practical side:

Description of the characteristics of the study sample:

Table (1) shows the description of the characteristics of the demographic study sample represented in job title, age, gender, educational level and years of experience in the health sector (n=100).

Table (1) Distribution of Study Sample by Demographic Characteristics (Sample Size 100).

Table 1: Distribution of the study sample according to personal variables (n=100)

Demographic variables	Iteration	Percentage %	
Job title	- Doctor	5	05
	- Administrative	25	25
	- Nursing	32	32
	- Pharmacist	06	06
	- Technician	32	32
Age	- 30 years and less	40	40
	- 31 to 50	50	50
	- 51 and mor	10	10
Gender	- Male	35	35
	- Female	65	65
educational level	- High school and below	18	18
	- Diploma, Bachelor	76	76
	- postgraduate studies	6	06
Years of Experience	- 1-5 years	39	39
	- 6-10 years	37	37
	- More than 10 years	24	24

Table (1) indicates that the percentage of males in the study sample reached (35%) while the percentage of females reached (65%). As for the distribution of the study sample by age, Table (1) indicates that the percentage of workers in the study sample whose age falls in the age group (less than 30 years) has reached (40%). While the percentage of employees in the age group (31-50 years) (50%). The percentage of employees in the study sample in each of the two groups (51 years and over) was (10%). With regard to the distribution of the study sample by educational level, Table (1) indicates that (76%) of the of the study sample hold a first university degree (bachelor's) and Diploma, while the percentage of employees holding master's and doctoral degrees (postgraduate studies) was (6%). Table (1) also indicates a low percentage of employees in the study sample holding a high school diploma or less, as their percentage reached (18%).

With regard to the distribution of the study sample members according to the total year of experience, Table (1) shows that (37%) of the employees have a total experience ranging from (6-10 years). (39%) of employees have a total experience ranging from (1-5 years). (24%) of employees have total experience (more than 10 years).

Analysis and discussion the questions and hypothesis of the study

The first question: To what extent does training and development of human resources affect the achievement of total quality in health centers in the northern sector?

In order to answer the first question, the arithmetic averages and standard deviations were calculated for all paragraphs that measure the impact of development and training of workers in achieving total quality, Table (2) shows this.

Table 2: Arithmetic averages and standard deviations for all paragraphs that measure the extent of development and training of human resources affect the achievement of total quality in health centers in the northern sector?

No	Paragraphs	Arithmetic Averages	Standard Deviations	Degree of Approval
1	Quality-related training and development is available to all employees of the Health Directorate centers.	3.09	1.17	medium
2	There is satisfaction with the quality of training programs available to improve the quality of work	3.09	1.03	medium
3	There is satisfaction with the number of training and development programs available to providers.	3.04	1.05	medium
4	Technological and training availability to improve the quality of work	2.77	1.21	medium
5	Budgets allocated to education and training are sufficient to improve performance for all employees without bias.	2.65	1.10	medium
	The overall average	2.93	0.82	medium

It appears from Table (2) that the arithmetic averages of the paragraphs that measure the impact of development and training of workers in achieving total quality ranged between (3.09-2.65), the most prominent of which was paragraph No. (1,2), which states "Training and development related to quality is available to all workers in the centers of the Directorate of Health, and there is satisfaction with the quality of training programs available to improve the quality of work" and to a medium degree, then paragraph No. (3) came with an arithmetic average of (3.04) and with a medium degree, which states: "There is satisfaction with the number of training and development programs available to providers", and the lowest arithmetic averages of paragraph (5), which states "The budgets allocated to education and training are sufficient to improve performance for all employees without bias" came with an arithmetic average of (2.65) with a medium degree.

The overall average of the paragraphs that measure the impact of development and training of workers in achieving total quality was (2.93) with a medium

And the application of the (T) test for single samples (One- Sample t.Test) on the general average to measure the impact of development and training of workers in achieving total quality.

The first hypothesis. There is a statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for training and development in achieving total quality in health centers. Table (3) illustrates this.

Table 3: Results of the application of (T) test for single samples (One- Sample t.Test) on the general average to measure the impact of development and training of workers in achieving total quality

Dimension	Arithmetic Averages	Standard Deviations	T value	significant	Result
Development and training for employees	2.93	0.82	0.87-	0.38	reject

Table (3) shows that the value of (T) reached (-0.87) and statistically significant (0.38), where the general mean was compared with the standard value of the five-point scale, which is (3), and the results showed an average and non-statistically significant degree of the impact of development and training of workers in achieving total quality.

The second question: What is the role of motivation for human resources in achieving total quality in health centers in the northern sector?

Table 4: Arithmetic averages and standard deviations for all paragraphs that measure the role of motivation for human resources in achieving total quality in health centers in the northern sector

No.	Paragraphs	Arithmetic Averages	Standard Deviations	Degree of Approval
1	Incentives are a driver for quality improvement	4.29	0.95	High
2	Evaluate and motivate employees by subordinates fairly without personal worker intervention	3.41	1.35	medium
3	Personal achievement is rewarded, not group and comrades	3.25	1.31	medium
4	has already given you any motivation for a special work you have done and you feel that you deserve it	2.95	1.40	medium
	The overall average	3.48	0.81	medium

It appears from Table (4) that the arithmetic averages of the paragraphs that measure the extent to which the motivation of service providers affects the achievement of total quality ranged between (4.29-2.95), the most prominent of which was paragraph No. (1), which states "Incentives are a drive for quality improvement" and to a high degree, then paragraph No. (2) came with an arithmetic average of (3.41) and with a medium degree, which states: "Evaluate and motivate employees by subordinates fairly without personal worker intervention", and the lowest arithmetic averages came for paragraph No. (4), which states "Previously Give you any motivation for a special work you have done and you feel you deserve it" with an arithmetic average of (2.95) with an average score.

The overall average of the paragraphs that measure the impact of the employee motivation in achieving total quality was (3.48) with a medium degree.

And the application of the (T) test for single samples (One- Sample t.Test) on the general average to measure the effect of motivation in achieving total quality in health centers.

The second hypothesis: There is a statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of motivation in achieving total quality in health centers. Table (5) illustrates this.

Table 5: Results of the application of the (T) test for single samples (One- Sample t.Test) on the general average to measure the effect the motivation of service providers in achieving total quality

Dimension	Arithmetic Averages	Standard Deviations	T value	Significant	Result
Motivation for Service Providers	3.48	0.81	5.85	0.00	accept

Table (5) shows that the value of (T) reached (5.85) and statistically significant (0.00), where the general mean was compared with the standard value of the five-point scale which is (3), and the results showed a statistically significant degree of the effect of motivating service providers in achieving total quality.

The third question: What is the role of guidance for human resources in achieving total quality in health centers in the northern sector?

Table 6: Arithmetic averages and standard deviations for all paragraphs that measure the role of guidance for human resources in achieving total quality in health centers in the northern sector?

No.	Paragraphs	Arithmetic Averages	Standard Deviations	Degree of Approval
1	Helps old employees (with long service and experience) in guiding new employees without prejudice	3.40	1.28	medium
2	Guidelines are available to enhance the efficiency of performance and quality of work for new employees	3.05	1.20	medium
3	Ongoing mentoring programs are available for each new employee	2.99	1.28	medium
4	Training is carried out on quality means and tools during the mentoring and counseling process	2.88	1.19	medium
	The overall average	3.08	0.97	medium

It appears from Table (6) that the arithmetic averages of the paragraphs that measure the impact of attention to the element of guidance to achieve total quality ranged between (3.40-2.88), the most prominent of which was paragraph No. (1), which states "Helps old employees (with long service and experience) in guiding new employees without bias" and to a medium degree, then paragraph No. (2) came with an arithmetic average of (3.05) and with a medium degree, which states: "Guidelines are available to enhance the efficiency of performance and quality of work for new employees", and the lowest arithmetic averages of paragraph No. (4), which states "Training on quality means and tools during the guidance and guidance process" came with an arithmetic average of (2.88) with an average score.

The overall average of the paragraphs that measure the impact of attention to the element of guidance to achieve total quality was (3.08) and to a medium degree.

And the application of the (T) test for single samples (One- Sample t.Test) on the general average to measure the effect of guidance process in achieving total quality in health centers.

The third hypothesis: There is a statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of guidance in achieving total quality in health centers.

Table 7: Results of the application of (T) test for single samples (One- Sample t.Test) on the general average to measure the effect the element of guidance to achieve total quality

Dimension	Arithmetic Averages	Standard Deviations	T value	Significant	Result
Guidance	3.08	0.97	0.82	0.41	reject

Table (7) shows that the value of (T) amounted to (0.82) and statistically significant (0.41), where the general mean was compared with the standard value of the five-point scale, which is (3), and the results showed an average and non-statistically significant degree of the impact of attention to the element of guidance in achieving total quality.

The Fourth question: What is the role of employee's relations in achieving total quality in health centers in the northern sector?

Table 8: Arithmetic averages and standard deviations for all paragraphs that measure the role of the employee's relationship in achieving total quality in health centers in the northern sector

No.	Paragraphs	Arithmetic Averages	Standard Deviations	Degree of Approval
1	The employee relationship is an effective element in business continuity	4.35	1.28	high
2	Negative relationships between employees affect the service forum.	4.28	0.98	high
3	Discrimination between employees affects the level of performance of employees	4.26	1.07	high
4	The employee relationship is an effective element in quality development	4.23	1.08	high
	The overall average	4.28	0.97	high

It appears from Table (8) that the arithmetic averages of the paragraphs that measure the impact of the employee relationship in achieving total quality ranged between (4.35-4.23), the most prominent of which was paragraph No. (1), which states: "The employee relationship is an effective element in business continuity" and to a high degree, then paragraph No. (2) came with an arithmetic average (4.28) and with a high degree, which states: "Negative relationships between employees affect the service forum", and the lowest arithmetic averages came for paragraph No. (4), which states: "The employee relationship is an Effective element in developing quality" with an arithmetic average of (4.23) with a high degree.

The overall average of the paragraphs that measure the impact of the employee relationship in achieving total quality was (4.28) with a high degree.

And the application of the (T) test for single samples (One- Sample t.Test) on the general average to measure the effect of employee's relations in achieving total quality in health centers.

The fourth hypothesis: There is a statistically significant effect ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) of employee's relations in achieving total quality in health centers.

Table 9: Results of the application of (T) test for single samples (One- Sample t.Test) on the general average to measure the effect of the employee's relations in achieving total quality in health centers

Dimension	Arithmetic Averages	Standard Deviations	T value	Significant	Result
Employee Relationship	4.28	0.72	17.89	0.00	accept

Table (9) shows that the value of (T) reached (17.89) and in statistical significance (0.00), where the general mean was compared with the standard value of the five-point scale, which is (3), and the results showed a high and statistically significant degree of the impact of the employee relationship in achieving total quality.

FINDINGS

By presenting the values of the statistical analysis and answering the questions of the study, the results can be summarized as follows:

- 1- There is an average effect of training and development for workers in achieving total quality in health centers in Irbid Governorate, but it did not reach the level of statistical significance (0.05) and was approaching of (3), which is the value of the hypothetical mean of the five-gradient used, and therefore the impact did not reach the level of approved significance.

- 2- One of the most prominent effects in the field of development and training for workers to achieve total quality, is the presence of satisfaction with the quality of training programs available to improve the quality of work, and the training and development related to quality is available to all workers in the centers of the Directorate of Health.
- 3- The impact of the employee's relations in achieving total quality was high, as the total arithmetic average was (4.28) out of (5), which is a high value and indicates a clear and statistically significant impact.
- 4- The employee's relations are an effective element in business continuity, and the negative relations between employees affect the recipient of the service.
- 5- The impact of employee's motivation in achieving total quality was statistically significant, as the total arithmetic mean was (3.48) out of (5), which is a medium value, and indicates an impact of employee motivation in achieving total quality, and Incentives are a clear motivation for improving overall quality.
- 6- There is an average but not statistically significant effect of the guidance element in achieving total quality in health centers in Irbid Governorate, where the level of impact did not reach the level of statistical significance (0.05) and was close to (3), which is the value of the hypothetical mean of the five-gradient used. But Providing assistance by old employees (with long service and experience) in guiding new employees without prejudice, affecting the overall quality.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In light of the results of this study, a number of recommendations were proposed, most notably:

- 1- Conducting training courses to develop workers and increase their efficiency to achieve total quality in health centers.
- 2- Disbursement of rewards and incentives to encourage and motivate workers to work towards achieving total quality in health centers.
- 3- Review the financial allocations disbursed by subordinates to employees and disburse them fairly.
- 4- Benefiting from the expertise and competencies of old employees and helping them to new employees.
- 5- Preparing and implementing orientation workshops to enhance the efficiency of performance and quality of work for new employees.
- 6- Provide guidelines to enhance the efficiency of performance and quality of work for new employees.

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